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Environmental Marine Information System (EMIS) - A Geo-portal to assist in the management of European Seas and Global Ocean

--Manuscript Draft--

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Abstract:	<p>Abstract: Understanding the inner dynamics of European and global seas and coasts is essential to support political requirements underlined by marine and maritime policies, as well as to achieve commitments with regard to international conventions addressing biodiversity targets, climate change and efficient use of natural resources. The Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission in its role as a Competence Centre for the Marine Strategy Framework Directive has developed the Environmental Marine Information System (EMIS) to assist Member States with the monitoring and assessment of their marine and coastal waters in Europe and globally.</p> <p>EMIS provides the user community with a set of bio-physical information that is relying on data from Earth Observation satellites and oceanic models, and on derived indicators for the diagnostic of the coastal state and analyses of changes in marine ecosystems. Basic navigation and interrogation tools are additionally integrated in the system to automatically perform time-series and statistical analyses on any region of interest for reporting purposes.</p> <p>EMIS is a geo-portal implemented with services compliant with the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) specifications and INSPIRE standards to ensure full interoperability. These services are connected to R-written functions, enabling the processing of EMIS data, their analysis and reporting to be integrated in a unique development environment in support of the EU marine policies. Through the EMIS Marine Analyst, an example of such reporting is provided for a marine protected area in the Mediterranean Sea.</p>
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6 **Environmental Marine Information System – A geo-portal to assist in the management**
7 **of European Seas and global ocean**

8

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26 targets, climate change and efficient use of natural resources. The Joint Research Centre (JRC)
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37 Consortium (OGC) specifications and INSPIRE standards to ensure full interoperability. These
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39 analysis and reporting to be integrated in a unique development environment in support of the
40 EU marine policies. Through the EMIS Marine Analyst, an example of such reporting is
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45

46 **Introduction**

47 Rapid and often negative changes at large scale of the water quality, and subsequent
48 degradation of marine habitats have triggered the necessity to develop strong political
49 instruments that would preserve the natural resources and biodiversity of the seas, while
50 keeping the marine-related economic sectors viable. For example, the Marine Strategy
51 Framework Directive (MSFD), adopted in 2008 (EC 2008) and legislated in 2010 (EU 2010a),
52 aims to achieve good environmental status (GES) of European marine and coastal waters by
53 2020, adopting an ecosystem approach to the management of human activities that impact the
54 marine environment. The implementation of this directive requires systematic measurements
55 of biotic and abiotic parameters associated with 11 descriptors formally identified (EC 2008,
56 Annex 1) to guide the assessment of GES. In turn, the success of implementing this directive
57 depends on the nature and reliability of scientific data, the aggregation of these data into
58 appropriate information (indicator) maps, as well as the degree of harmonization in the methods
59 and monitoring tools, and on the frequency to which this information can be made available to
60 the stakeholders with respect to the time variability of marine processes.

61 Over the last two decades, earth observation from satellite has demonstrated great potential to
62 capture important marine and coastal processes like sediment transport, coastal upwelling
63 (Hoepffner et al. 2014), eutrophication (Gohin et al. 2008; Terauchi et al. 2014), population
64 dynamics and ecosystem shifts (Koeller et al. 2009), over extensive areas and at time scale
65 ranging from hours to several days or years. Satellite-based optical and infrared sensors provide
66 a unique synoptic-scale approach to characterize the pelagic ecosystem through mapping
67 biologically important variables such as phytoplankton biomass, primary production (Saba et
68 al. 2011; Mélin and Hoepffner 2011), and phytoplankton assemblages (Goela et al. 2015),
69 representing critical elements of the Earth's carbon budget and biogeochemical cycles. In
70 addition, these variables are descriptors of the first trophic level in the marine food chain. Their

71 estimates from satellite therefore provide essential information on the structure, distribution
72 and functioning of the rest of the food web, including commercially exploited fish populations
73 (Chassot et al. 2010; Druon et al. 2016).

74 In spite of the great potential of satellite data to achieve synoptic examination of the global
75 ocean and coastal areas, there are still some constraints in using these data operationally,
76 including uneasy access to the data and inadequate analysis and information dissemination
77 approaches to communities outside the research and scientific institutions. Systems to handle
78 geographical or spatial data have however evolved rapidly during the last decade towards
79 efficient analysis tools of marine and coastal ecosystems that integrate functionalities such as
80 database creation, monitoring, mapping and visualization. Geographical Information Systems
81 (GIS), for example, enable the combination of data from multiple and disparate sources, and
82 provide excellent platforms to communicate results of scientific analysis to a wider community
83 including policy makers. Through different case studies, Stojanovic, Green, and Lymbery
84 (2010) showed all the benefits of local and regional information systems to improve the
85 management of marine and coastal environment, creating suitable architectures bringing
86 together data and information that would otherwise be lost into disconnected, or even
87 antagonistic, framework.

88 This work reviews the features of a marine and coastal information system, designed to provide
89 the user community appropriate information to conduct water quality assessment and resource
90 monitoring in the coastal and marine waters around Europe and globally. The Environmental
91 Marine Information System (EMIS; <http://emis.jrc.ec.europa.eu>) has been developed as part of
92 the institutional activities of the European Commission – Joint Research Centre as a
93 contribution to the Europe 2020 objectives (EU 2010b) of a “smart, sustainable and inclusive
94 growth”. Through the analysis of satellite data and modeling outputs, illustrated by a case-
95 study of a marine protected area in the Mediterranean Sea, we highlight the benefits of EMIS

96 for Member States and other bodies as a tool to support an effective and long-lasting
97 stewardship of EU seas and global ocean by providing scientific and technical value-added
98 products to assist Member States and other bodies with cost-effective monitoring and
99 comparable assessment of environmental status of their marine waters.

100

101 **EMIS web-GIS Design and Architecture**

102 The EMIS Web-GIS application is based on a MapServer engine, an open source geographic
103 data delivering engine with integrated GDAL (Geospatial Data Abstraction Library), originally
104 developed by the University of Minnesota (UMN), for building spatially enabled web
105 applications. UMN MapServer (v.6.4) allows creating geographic image maps, as well as to
106 browse and query the database. Scripts are written in PHP Hypertext Pre-processor and in
107 Perl/Python/R programming languages for developing server-side applications and dynamic
108 web content. The interaction with MapServer engine is achieved using PHP/MapScript, a
109 dynamically loadable module that makes MapServer's functions and classes available in a PHP
110 environment. Access to the scientific datasets is done through file system (noSQL).

111 To ensure full interoperability with other GIS systems, EMIS is implemented with Open
112 Geospatial Consortium (OGC)-compliant services and INSPIRE standards (EC 2007). In
113 particular, OGC Web Coverage Service (WCS 1.0.0) and its tiling scheme facilitate the
114 publication and exchange of geospatial data with space and time-varying features. Moreover,
115 EMIS is compliant to the EU programme on interoperability solutions and common framework
116 for European public administrations, businesses and citizens (ISA² Programme; EU 2015),
117 which supports the development of digital solutions allowing interoperable cross-border and
118 cross-sector public services.

119 These services are connected to R-written functions, enabling the remote processing of EMIS
120 data, their analysis and reporting to be integrated in a unique development environment.

121 **EMIS Database and Processing**

122 Most of the data populating the geo-portal are derived from Earth Observing satellites,
123 specifically those carrying optical and infrared radiometers. To complement these data, EMIS-
124 Europe also includes physical variables derived from a numerical model simulating most
125 relevant hydro- and thermodynamic processes in marine and coastal waters, as well as
126 advanced bio-indicators of the environmental status of the water column and seabed that often
127 are derived from the combination of satellite and model products.

128 *Satellite Observations*

129 Satellite data within EMIS rely on three major ocean colour missions, the on-going Moderate
130 Resolution Spectroradiometer on board Aqua (MODIS-Aqua; Esaias et al. 1998), the Sea-
131 viewing Wide Field-of-View Sensor 1997-2010 (SeaWiFS; McClain et al. 1998) and the
132 Medium Resolution Imaging Spectrometer 2002-2012 (MERIS; Rast, Bezy, and Bruzzi 1999).
133 European products in EMIS have been processed starting from the raw Level-1 top-of-
134 atmosphere radiances at different wavelengths to create biogeochemical data on a spatial grid
135 of 2-km and 4-km bin size centered over Europe. Global products at a coarser resolution (4-
136 km or 9-km bin size) have been obtained directly from the US National Aeronautics and Space
137 Administration (NASA) in the form of binned Level-3 data and subsequently re-mapped on to
138 the EMIS domain grid. In all cases, satellite scenes are (re)-processed with the latest version of
139 the SeaWiFS Data Analysis System (SeaDAS) software (Fu, Baith, and McClain 1998).
140 From the sea surface reflectance, a number of bio-optical and biogeochemical products (Table
141 1) are derived using standard (i.e., operated by space agencies) and in-house peer-reviewed
142 algorithms, which have been implemented in a fully operational processing chain for
143 application in the global ocean and European seas (Vantrepotte and Mélin 2010; Mélin et al.
144 2011).

145 **Table 1:** Satellite-derived marine products as presently available in EMIS. Note that the
 146 database for EMIS is updated on regular basis to extend time-series from on-going
 147 sensors, as well as to include products from new sensors / algorithms.

EMIS satellite products	Sensors	Spatio-temporal coverage			
		Global		Europe	
		9km	4km	4km	2km
Surface chlorophyll concentration	MODIS-Acqua	2002-2016	2002-2016	2002-2012	2002-2015
	SeaWiFS	1997-2010	1997-2010	1997-2004	1997-2004
	MERIS	2002-2012	2002-2012	2002-2011	2002-2011
	VIIRS		2012-2015		
Diffuse attenuation coefficient at 490nm (Kd_{490})	MODIS-Acqua	2002-2016	2002-2016	2002-2012	2002-2009
	SeaWiFS	1997-2010	1997-2010	1997-2004	1997-2004
	MERIS	2002-2012	2002-2012	2002-2011	2002-2011
Photosynthetically active radiation (PAR)	MODIS-Acqua	2002-2012	2002-2012	2002-2012	-
	SeaWiFS	1997-2010	1997-2010	1997-2004	1997-2004
Phytoplankton absorption coefficient at 443nm	MODIS-Acqua	2002-2012	2002-2012	2002-2012	-
	SeaWiFS	1997-2010	1997-2010	-	-
	MERIS	-	-	2002-2011	2002-2011
Detritus and CDOM absorption coefficient at 443nm	MODIS-Acqua	2002-2012	2002-2012	2002-2012	-
	SeaWiFS	1997-2010	1997-2010	-	-
Particulate backscatter coefficient at 443nm	MODIS-Acqua	2002-2012	2002-2012	2002-2012	-
	SeaWiFS	1997-2010	1997-2010	-	-
	MERIS	-	-	2002-2011	2002-2011
Surface productive layer (euphotic zone)	MERIS	-	-	2002-2011	2002-2011
Primary production	SeaWiFS	1997-2007	-	1997-2008	-
Sea surface temperature	MODIS-Terra	2000-2016	2000-2016	2000-2016	2000-2012
	NOAA Pathfinder	1981-2009	1981-2009	1981-2009	-

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 149
 150 Other satellite sensors include the Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR)
 151 Pathfinder series 1981-2012 (v.5.2) and the on-going MODIS onboard Terra. The combination
 152 of both sensors is granting a time-series of sea surface temperature (SST) since 1985. The data
 153 (Table 1) are also obtained as binned files from NASA and re-mapped on the domain grid. The

154 satellite dataset consists of monthly composites covering the European seas at large (70°N –
155 10°N Lat.; 30°W – 42°E) and the global ocean. The database from ocean colour and thermal
156 radiometry is updated on a regular basis to include either data from new sensors, data recently
157 acquired from existing sensors, or data re-processed by space agencies.

158 Particular attention is made to the quality of the information provided. Validation exercises are
159 regularly performed to assess the efficiency and accuracy of satellite data over European seas
160 (Zibordi et al. 2013), using in situ geographically distributed bio-optical measurements
161 collected in different marine regions as part of the JRC programme Bio-optical Mapping of
162 Marine Properties (BioMAP; Zibordi et al. 2011). Globally, ocean colour data from satellite
163 are validated through the AERONET-OC system (Zibordi et al. 2009) producing standardized
164 optical measurements at fixed platforms deployed at sites with different water characteristics.

165

166 *Modeling Outputs*

167 Within EMIS-Europe, a set of marine physical variables is generated from a freely available
168 General Estuarine Transport Model (GETM), a 3-D hydrodynamic model described in details
169 by (Burchard and Bolding 2002). GETM is operated with a flexible vertical and horizontal
170 coordinate system, enabling applications in shallow coastal environments. It also benefits from
171 an accurate turbulence parameterization scheme through its coupling with the General Ocean
172 Turbulence Model (GOTM; Burchard 2002). The model is consistently implemented for most
173 of the European seas, including the northeastern Atlantic from 32°N to 61°N of latitude and
174 extending to 13°W in longitude. Its outputs have been validated through several studies in the
175 North Sea (Stips et al. 2004), the Black Sea (Peneva and Stips 2005), the Mediterranean Sea
176 (Garcia-Gorriz and Stips 2006; Macias-Moy, Garcia-Gorriz , and Stips 2015) and the Baltic
177 Sea (Miladinova and Stips 2010). Modeled data are complementing satellite observations to
178 provide the vertical structure of the water column in terms of, e.g., mixed layer depth, surface

179 and bottom salinity, mean temperature, variables that are often used to derive indices of key
 180 processes occurring at the surface, as well as on the seabed.

181

182 ***Indicators for Policy Support***

183 Environmental or ecological indicators are essential to assess ecosystem health, strength and
 184 resilience (Platt et al. 2009; Borja et al. 2016). They can turn scientific data into objective well-
 185 understood and widely accepted metrics to detect changes occurring in response to
 186 environmental perturbations. In Europe, the marine directive MSFD (EC 2008) aims to achieve
 187 good environmental status of European marine waters by 2020, applying an ecosystem
 188 approach to human activities on the basis of eleven descriptors. Each of these descriptors is
 189 associated with a number of indicators (Zampoukas et al. 2012) describing the state of the
 190 environment with respect to that descriptor. EMIS products can contribute significantly to
 191 monitor the state of the marine environments regarding its physical and biological properties
 192 and at time and spatial scales compatible with MSFD requirements (Table 2). The system is,
 193 in fact, increasingly used to foster sustainable management of the marine and coastal resources,
 194 including fisheries.

195

196 **Table 2.** Links between EMIS products and descriptors and associated indicators of the Marine
 197 Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD).

EMIS products	Marine Information	Support to MSFD descriptors / indicators (as listed in EU 2010)
Chlorophyll-a	Proxy for phytoplankton biomass	D1 / 1.6.2; 1.7.1 D4 / 4.3.1 D5 / 5.2.1
Diffuse attenuation Coefficient (490 nm)	Proxy for water transparency	D1 / 1.6.3 D5 / 5.2.2
Productive layer	Extent of the euphotic (sunlight) zone	D1 / 1.6.3
Bathymetry	Water depth, seabed topography	D1 / 1.6.3 D7 / 7.2.2

Mixed layer depth	Water column mixing characteristics	D1 / 1.6.3
Maximum density gradient	Water column mixing characteristics	D1 / 1.6.3
Physically sensitive Area index (PSA)	Vulnerability to eutrophication	D5 monitoring
OXYRISK	Oxygen depletion risk index at depth	D5 / 5.3.2 monitoring
Water temperature (SST and bottom temperature)	Hydrographical conditions	D1 / 1.6.3
Bottom salinity	Hydrographical conditions	D1 / 1.6.3
Seabed habitat	Extent and proportion of benthic habitats	D1 / 1.4.1; 1.4.2; 1.5.1; 1.5.2; 1.7.1 D6 / 6.1.1; 6.1.2
Spawning habitat (bluefin tuna)	Extent of potential spawning habitat	D1 / 1.5.1 D3 / 3.2.1 monitoring
Feeding habitat (bluefin & skipjack tuna, hake, fin whale)	Extent of potential feeding habitat	D1 / 1.5.1 D3 / 3.2.1 monitoring

198

199 Two indicators addressing eutrophication in European coastal areas have been integrated into
200 EMIS, following the description by Druon et al. (2004) and Djavidnia et al. (2005). The
201 Physically Sensitive Area index (PSA) measures the physical resistance to eutrophication (i.e.
202 oxygen deficiency), assuming that phytoplankton growth and oxygen cycle are primarily
203 controlled by physical conditions. The PSA index takes into consideration surface and bottom
204 physics, as well as the dynamics in the upper water column. The Oxygen Risk depletion index
205 (Oxyrisk) measures the probability to have oxygen deficiency at the sea bottom of coastal areas
206 (water depth below 100m) due to the degradation of organic matter. The Oxyrisk index
207 combines satellite estimates of primary production and numerical modeling of the physical
208 capacity of oxygen renewal near the sea-bottom (by vertical mixing).

209 Potential habitat maps of key predators which highlight the importance of productive fronts for
210 feeding are also included in EMIS. Chlorophyll-a fronts are indeed highly dynamic features
211 that were shown to be hotspots of marine productivity as they stand long enough (weeks to
212 months) to efficiently transfer the energy in marine food webs through zooplankton growth
213 and to attract higher trophic levels, e.g., the Atlantic bluefin tuna (Druon et al. 2016), fin whales

214 (Druon et al. 2012), hake recruits (Druon et al. 2015). Maps of preferred habitats of these key
 215 marine fish species have been integrated in EMIS (Table 3) at spatial and temporal resolution
 216 relevant for a dynamic management of fisheries and marine ecosystems in general. They cover
 217 European seas, as well as different parts of the global ocean. Ecological niche modelling (ENM
 218 [17]) was used to predict the potential feeding (and eventually spawning) habitat of these
 219 species. ENMs are spatially-explicit methods that use the ecological requirements of a given
 220 species to predict its potential distribution in space and time. In particular, this ENM approach
 221 uses presence or abundance data to bridge knowledge on specific ecological traits (e.g.
 222 mobility, feeding strategy) with patterns of selected environmental variables (e.g. chlorophyll-
 223 a fronts and concentration, surface or bottom temperature or current velocity). As a result of
 224 the modelling analysis, all studied top predators were sighted in the vicinity of chlorophyll-a
 225 fronts with relatively low chlorophyll levels ($< 0.5 \text{ mg.m}^{-3}$) in relation to the feeding behaviour.

226

227 **Table 3.** Description by fish species of favorable habitats products presently inserted within
 228 EMIS.

Fish species	Habitat type	Area covered	Period covered
Atlantic Bluefin tuna (adults)	Feeding and spawning	North Atlantic, Mediterranean Sea	2003-2013
Atlantic Bluefin tuna (juveniles)	Feeding	North Atlantic, Mediterranean Sea	2003-2013
Skipjack tuna	Feeding	Central east Atlantic	1998-2013
Hake nurseries	Feeding	Mediterranean Sea	2003-2015
Fin whale	Feeding	West Mediterranean Sea	2003-2015

229

230 Other indicators are the anomalies of satellite-derived variables. Monthly anomalies have been
 231 calculated by subtracting climatological values of each month over the entire time-series from
 232 the monthly observed data. These climate-related indicators are important to detect changing
 233 patterns of the environment (Gregg and Rousseaux 2014), and significant deviations from long-

234 term average causing damage of the ecosystems that may be irreversible (e.g. coral bleaching;
235 Pratchett et al. 2011).

236

237 EMIS System Functionalities

238 The EMIS Web-GIS viewer (Fig. 1) offers a wide set of tools which allow discovery,
239 navigation and browsing through the data in different ways according to the considered spatial
240 resolution, the variable to be analysed (physical or biological), and the time period (year and
241 month or month only for climatology datasets). Using the control panel or directly with the
242 cursor, the map can be centred and/or zoomed to the region of interest. In addition, many
243 regions are predefined in the system directing the users to their preferred area.

244 **Figure 1.** Web-GIS viewer layout structure. 1. Display window; 2. Control bar (selection of
245 variables with time and spatial attributes; navigation and data interrogating tools); 3. Left menu
246 panel (detailed elements of each of the 4 tool bar options); 4. Data dissemination tool panel.
247
248

249
250 Another set of applications has been developed to query the data and perform statistical
251 analysis on the region of interest (i.e., single pixel or box area). Basic statistics include the
252 mean, minimum and maximum values and the standard deviation of the selected variable. An
253 arithmetic or geometric mean is calculated according to the type of distribution of the variable
254 (i.e., normal or log-normal distribution). To avoid outlier pixels in the calculation of the mean,
255 a two-step ‘pixel filtering’ is applied to the data by rejecting from the calculation all values
256 outside a distance of 2 times the standard deviation around the mean.

257 Among other statistical features, a threshold analysis allows the display of values within a
258 selected range. This function is particularly interesting to highlight mesoscale features affecting
259 the variable displayed on the map. Correlation analysis can be made between two selected
260 variables, resulting in a scatter plot or a 2D density plot depending on whether the total number
261 of sampled pixels is lower or larger than 5000. Finally, time series and inter-annual monthly
262 variability analysis can be performed on a selected marine variable. All data analysis can be
263 visualized either as charts or graphs in the display area and the resulting data are also available
264 as ASCII file for further analysis and investigation. The EMIS GIS viewer provides additional
265 functions to download datasets in different formats (e.g. netCDF, GeoTIFF), to print maps and
266 to download results directly to PDF files.

267

268 **EMIS Web Services**

269 Due to the growing and successful launches of earth observation satellites and increasing
270 capacity of ocean model to realistically capture the marine physics and ecosystem dynamics,
271 we process increasingly larger volumes of scientific data making use of progressively more
272 relevant environmental information. The dramatic increase of available data sets, together with
273 the plurality of data providers, poses a challenge for integrating and making valuable use of
274 the information produced. Data and interface standards have the great advantage of defining a

275 “*lingua-franca*” for different systems, organizations and users to share and exchange
 276 information, while avoiding duplications. In the geospatial domain a platform based on
 277 interoperable and harmonized services and data is called Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI). In
 278 addition to the GIS viewer, EMIS SDI (Fig.2) includes a Discovery tool, a Marine Analyst tool
 279 and a Marine Maps Platform to support the assessment and the monitoring of the environmental
 280 state and marine biodiversity of the European regional seas and global ocean.

281

282 **Figure 2.** Architecture and technical workflow of the Geoportal EMIS and its associated
 283 tools.

284

285 ***Data Discovery Tool***

286 According to both the interoperability subsidiary principle and best practice recommendations,
 287 the description of the data (i.e. the metadata) is made available and distributed to all interested
 288 users and/or other systems in order to share the knowledge of these existing data throughout
 289 the community. This is done through a metadata repository, i.e. a query-able catalogue.

290 A user of the EMIS geoportal is thus able to search (i.e. discover) what metadata is available
291 using a dedicated catalogue. This also means that once a discovery query is launched through
292 the geoportals, the user will be returned all (or part) of the available metadata information.
293 EMIS is implemented with a number of metadata elements that are common to the ocean
294 science community, with full compatibility of standards guaranteeing the interoperability of
295 systems. The Discovery tool enables an easy and fast visualisation of EMIS database and
296 proposes shortcuts to ease a direct access and download of a selected dataset in three different
297 ways: display (GIS viewer, WMS), download (netCDF, GeoTIFF, WCS), and query of
298 metadata (CSW).

299 ***Marine Analyst***

300 The EMIS Marine Analyst tool was developed to support the assessment and monitoring of the
301 environmental status and trends of any pre-defined marine areas, including marine protected
302 areas (MPAs) in Europe and globally. The tool is derived from open source R libraries (EMIS-
303 R; <https://github.com/ldbk/EMISR>), implemented in the core of the EMIS server. The tool is
304 extracting raster data from EMIS (using WCS-T service) to derive images and statistics. For
305 example, following the user's selection of a given area or MPA (as extracted from the UNEP-
306 WCMC World Database on protected Areas), the tool is analyzing in real-time its
307 environmental status taking into consideration the variables included in EMIS. The final
308 outcome is given under the format of a report that includes the geographical and bathymetry
309 mapping of the MPA, a range of statistical analysis and time-series plots of the selected
310 variables, as well as a decadal series of monthly maps by variable. The report also includes
311 information on seabed structures and ecosystems, habitats, and density of alien species in the
312 MPA and surrounding waters. In addition to the report, the user has the possibility to open the
313 EMIS GIS viewer to do further analysis on the area of interest using other datasets available
314 within EMIS. A full application of this tool is given in a following section.

315 ***Marine Maps Platform***

316 This section points to a structure developed on the basis of open source systems using
317 GeoNode. The EMIS-Marine Maps complies with a number of standards and recommendations
318 in relation to the following three topics:

- 319 i) Metadata: These are the elements, which describe the data in terms of general resource
320 information like: title, geographic bounding box (area of interest), keywords, date of
321 publication, etc.
- 322 ii) Network Services: These are the services (typically web based) necessary to access and
323 deliver the data produced by the data center, e.g. Discovery, View, Download,
324 Transformation, etc.
- 325 iii) Data Specification: These are the common set of data models (and formats) necessary for
326 storing and exchanging data and information.

327 The Marine Maps platform brings a number of functional improvements to EMIS that facilitate
328 greater collaborative work, such as the ability for the users to create a working environment
329 using maps and/or documents already in place in various platforms and to upload its own
330 environmental data. Marine Maps also adds new functionality of its own, including enhanced
331 search and query capabilities for map layers, PostGIS integration, and additional map creation
332 features. It has been implemented with the objective to expand data collection from in-house
333 to remote sources and to optimize interactive tools allowing users to discover, combine, and
334 visualize materials from different sources and formats.

335

336 **Support to the Management of a Marine Protected Area (Marine Analyst Case Study)**

337 An increasing number of legislations and agreements (from national to global level) were
338 created and implemented to protect the marine environment against various human pressures.
339 These regulations highlight the necessity to develop integrated tools that help assessing and

340 monitoring the sustainable use of the marine resources with a particular focus on maintaining
341 biodiversity. Marine protected areas (MPAs) have been proposed throughout the world as an
342 optimal way to protect marine ecosystems (Lubchenco et al. 2003) becoming a key tool in
343 conservation programs for the marine environment, e.g. Target 11 of the Strategic Plan for
344 Biodiversity (CBD 2010) and the Sustainable Development Goal #14 (SDG 2015). In this
345 study, we have used the EMIS Marine Analyst tool to assess the environmental conditions
346 within and around the protected area of “Bouches de Bonifacio, Iles des Moines”(BBIM) in
347 the Mediterranean Sea (southern tip of Corsica, France, see fig 3). The marine protected area
348 BBIM is an area of ca. 950 km² classified as natural reserve since 1999 and integrated since
349 2015 within the Natura 2000 network as Zone of Special Conservation (ZSC) complying with
350 the EU Habitat Directive (EC 1992).

351

352

353 **Figure 3.** Local map of the protected area “Bouches de Bonifacio, Iles des Moines”. The area
354 is 100% marine located at the southern tip of Corsica and includes waters surrounding the small
355 islands “Ilots des Moines”.

356

357 The area is part of the Bonifacio Strait between Corsica and Sardinia distant of 16 km.
358 Maximum water depth in the central part of the Strait is 100 m, but increasing rapidly on the
359 west side to few thousands meters. The marine Analyst report includes 2-D (not shown) and 3-
360 D bathymetry maps of the area (fig. 4), created from the last 2016 release of EMODnet DTM
361 product (<http://www.emodnet-hydrography.eu>) covering European seas at ca. 230 m grid
362 resolution. The 3-D maps are given in 4 different perspectives (only 2 showed here) , enabling
363 a better vision of the topography on either side of the MPA.

364

365 **Figure 4.** 3D-viewing of the local bathymetry within and around the marine protected area
366 “Bouches de Bonifacio, Iles des Moines”.

367

368 The report also provides the EUNIS-compliant information on seabed habitats complemented
369 with geospatial information from the UNEP’s Global Seafloor Geomorphic Features Map
370 (GSGFM) following a methodology described by Tempera (2015). The MPA area is
371 characterized by a large variety of seabed structures profitable to different ecosystems (fig. 4).
372 Posidonia beds extend along the coast of Corsica and Sardinia, lying on infralittoral coarse
373 sediment. The ecosystem progressively shifts from coastal to shelf-edge detritic bottoms
374 communities on either side of the strait between both islands.

375

376

377

378 **Figure 5.** Local map of seabed habitats obtained by aggregation of two sources of
 379 information: EUNIS seafloor habitat classes and UNEP's Global seafloor Geomorphic
 380 features map, as described in Tempera (2015).

381

382 Together with such structural aspects of the area, the marine analyst reports on a series of
 383 environmental variables, under the form of maps and statistics, that are relevant to monitor
 384 potential changes in the state of the ecosystems, biodiversity and water quality within and
 385 around the MPA. The variables are either satellite-derived (e.g. sea surface temperature,
 386 chlorophyll concentration) or model-derived (e.g. mixed layer depth, bottom temperature and

387 salinity). Figure 6 shows maps of monthly SST (fig. 6a from MODIS-Terra) and chlorophyll
 388 time series (fig. 6b from MODIS-Aqua) for the last decadal period 2005-2015 at 4 km
 389 resolution. The seasonal variability of both variables is highly visible on these maps with
 390 maximum SST in July and August coinciding with minimum concentrations of surface
 391 chlorophyll content. Maximum chlorophyll concentrations are observed in March with a
 392 growing period lasting all winter months. For the entire time-series, mean values for SST and
 393 Chla over the entire period are 18.28 ± 4.27 °C and 0.32 ± 0.27 mg.m⁻³, respectively.
 394

395

397 **Figure 6.** (a) Time-series of monthly sea surface temperature (SST, in °C) as derived from
 398 MODIS-Terra sensor for the period 2005-2015. (b) Time-series of monthly chlorophyll a
 399 concentration (in mg.m⁻³) as derived from the sensor MODIS-Aqua for the period 2005-2015.

400

401 Figures 7 shows the monthly anomalies of both variables over the entire period of analysis.

402 These maps are important in terms of monitoring and managing MPAs' ecosystem, allowing

403 the identification of substantial deviations of the environment from natural variability. For

404 example, several negative anomaly events in sea surface temperature can be detected within

405 and around the MPA area (fig. 7a), with a difference of more than 1.5°C compared to

406 climatology. The strongest negative anomalies were recorded in June 2013 and July 2014, with
 407 deviations of -1.69°C and -1.68°C , respectively. These events are contrasting with the positive
 408 anomalies observed in July 2006 and July 2015 where SST deviation with respect to
 409 climatology were as high as $+1.77^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $+1.86^{\circ}\text{C}$ within the protected area.
 410

411 **Figure 7a.** Maps of monthly sea surface temperature anomalies with respect to monthly
 412 climatology calculated over the full MODIS-Terra time series as available in EMIS (i.e.
 413 complete years from 2001 to 2016).

414

415 Apparently, these anomalies in SST are not really impacting the concentrations of chlorophyll-
 416 a, showing no specific deviations from climatology at these two periods (fig. 7b). On the other

417 hand, a significant positive anomaly is observed in March-April 2005 and March 2010 with a
 418 difference in chlorophyll-a concentration of more than 0.6 mg.m^{-3} compared to climatology.
 419 These unusual chlorophyll highs have been reported in previous studies and explained by local
 420 and regional hydrodynamic factors. Becagli et al. (2013) has linked the 2005 spring bloom to
 421 a strong negative North Atlantic Oscillation phase. Casella et al. (2014) observed a higher
 422 number of eddies in early 2010 in the Liguro-Provençal basin compared to the previous year.
 423 These long-lived eddies contributed to major nutrient enrichment of the upper water column
 424 and subsequent enhancement of the phytoplankton spring bloom.
 425

426 **Figure 7b.** Maps of monthly chlorophyll-a anomalies with respect to monthly climatology
 427 calculated over the full MODIS-Aqua time series as available in EMIS (i.e. complete years
 428 from 2003 to 2016).

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The analysis of the surface variables observed from satellite is complemented with outcomes of 3D hydrodynamic model describing the water column and bottom physics. For example, monthly climatological values of the bottom salinity (fig.8a) and bottom temperature (fig.8b) are estimated over a decade period using the freely available General Estuarine Transport Model (GETM; <http://www.getm.eu>). The variability of these physical parameters is important to evaluate the status of benthic ecosystems within the protected area.

438 **Figure 8.** Monthly climatology of modeled bottom salinity (a) and bottom temperature (b)
439 within and around the BBIM marine protected area.

440

441 Another feature of the Marine Analyst is given in terms of alien species occurring in the MPA
442 (fig. 9) which are automatically extracted from the European Alien Species Information
443 network (EASIN; <http://easin.jrc.ec.europa.eu>). This network maintains an inventory of all
444 known alien and cryptogenic species in Europe as required by the Convention on Biological
445 Diversity and EU regulation on the prevention and management of the introduction and spread

446 of invasive alien species. A range number of alien species is given on a 10x10 km grid, with
 447 the species name possibly occurring in the studied area. For the Bonifacio MPA (fig.,9), alien
 448 species are listed as: *Asterionellopsis glacialis*, *Atherina boyeri*, *Cyprinus carpio*, *Haliotis*
 449 *tuberculata*, *Hexaplex trunculus*, *Potamopyrgus antipodarum*, *Prorocentrum minimum*, *P.*
 450 *triestinum*.

451

452

453 **Figure 9.** Density of alien species within and in the vicinity of the Bonifacio marine
 454 protected area. Data are extracted from the European Alien Species Information Network
 455 (EASIN).

456

457 The Marine Analyst is presently set up to provide the user with a prompt and concise
 458 information sheet on the environmental state of a given region of interest. To achieve this, the
 459 “on the fly” analyses of environmental data is limited to the last decade as observed by a
 460 specific sensor. However, the tool is directly linked to EMIS GIS viewer such that the user can
 461 complete the analysis of the area by applying the viewer-imbedded statistical tools to retrieve

462 the full time series of all data available for this region from one or multiple sensors, as well as
463 other products not delivered by the Marine Analyst tool. In addition to the environmental
464 features showed in this paper, the Marine Analyst reports on more products such as fish
465 habitats, and detailed statistics on each of the variables analysed.

466

467 **Conclusion**

468 The Environmental Marine Information System (EMIS) has features and components that are
469 specifically dedicated to assisting in the management of marine and coastal waters in Europe
470 and globally. The system provides an interoperable spatial data infrastructure platform enable
471 to integrate and disseminate the different spatial and referenced datasets and services in a
472 standardized way. The system supplies the users with: i) the provision of continuous, detailed
473 and accurate marine/coastal environmental data as derived from satellite observations (ocean
474 colour, sea surface temperature) and model outputs (bathymetry, hydrodynamics, habitats); ii)
475 the generation of indicators for the diagnosis of the coastal state and analyses of changes in
476 marine ecosystems (anomalies); iii) basic navigation and interrogation tools with elemental
477 statistics and time-series analysis. EMIS has the merit to actively support the implementation
478 of the EU marine directive as this system provides geo-spatial data that contribute to suitably
479 describe and monitor the environmental status of European Seas. Moreover, the EMIS Marine
480 Analyst, built around the R programming language, has been developed to, locally, explore
481 the EMIS marine database, restrict the data extraction to the selected area of interest and a
482 defined time period, and perform data analysis and indicator computation on-the-fly. The tool
483 was optimized for a large community of users and operates in a simple way as long as internet
484 access is available. In addition to the Marine Analyst report, the EMIS GIS viewer supplies the
485 user with further data analysis on the area of interest and provides added-value information on
486 the variables and potential links. The EMIS database and its associated tools and services are

487 updated on a regular basis to ensure best quality information for marine management.

488

489 **Acknowledgement**

490

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492 thanks all people having contributing to the development of EMIS either through the

493 provision of data or IT support. Space agencies are duly thanked for the distribution of

494 satellite data, in particular the Ocean Biology Processing Group of NASA.

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637

638 **Table 1:** Satellite-derived marine products as presently available in EMIS. Note that the

639 database for EMIS is updated on regular basis to extend time-series from on-going

640 sensors, as well as to include products from new sensors / algorithms.

641

EMIS satellite products	Sensors	Spatio-temporal coverage			
		Global		Europe	
		9km	4km	4km	2km
Surface chlorophyll concentration	MODIS-Acqua	2002-2016	2002-2016	2002-2012	2002-2015
	SeaWiFS	1997-2010	1997-2010	1997-2004	1997-2004
	MERIS	2002-2012	2002-2012	2002-2011	2002-2011
	VIIRS		2012-2015		
Diffuse attenuation coefficient at 490nm (Kd_{490})	MODIS-Acqua	2002-2016	2002-2016	2002-2012	2002-2009
	SeaWiFS	1997-2010	1997-2010	1997-2004	1997-2004
	MERIS	2002-2012	2002-2012	2002-2011	2002-2011
Photosynthetically active radiation (PAR)	MODIS-Acqua	2002-2012	2002-2012	2002-2012	-
	SeaWiFS	1997-2010	1997-2010	1997-2004	1997-2004
Phytoplankton absorption coefficient at 443nm	MODIS-Acqua	2002-2012	2002-2012	2002-2012	-
	SeaWiFS	1997-2010	1997-2010	-	-
	MERIS	-	-	2002-2011	2002-2011
Detritus and CDOM absorption coefficient at 443nm	MODIS-Acqua	2002-2012	2002-2012	2002-2012	-
	SeaWiFS	1997-2010	1997-2010	-	-
Particulate backscatter coefficient at 443nm	MODIS-Acqua	2002-2012	2002-2012	2002-2012	-
	SeaWiFS	1997-2010	1997-2010	-	-
	MERIS	-	-	2002-2011	2002-2011
Surface productive layer (euphotic zone)	MERIS	-	-	2002-2011	2002-2011
Primary production	SeaWiFS	1997-2007	-	1997-2008	-
Sea surface temperature	MODIS-Terra	2000-2016	2000-2016	2000-2016	2000-2012
	NOAA Pathfinder	1981-2009	1981-2009	1981-2009	-

642

643

644 **Table 2.** Links between EMIS products and descriptors and associated indicators of the
 645 Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD).

646

EMIS products	Marine Information	Support to MSFD descriptors / indicators (as listed in EU 2010)
Chlorophyll-a	Proxy for phytoplankton biomass	D1 / 1.6.2; 1.7.1 D4 / 4.3.1 D5 / 5.2.1
Diffuse attenuation Coefficient (490 nm)	Proxy for water transparency	D1 / 1.6.3 D5 / 5.2.2
Productive layer	Extent of the euphotic (sunlight) zone	D1 / 1.6.3
Bathymetry	Water depth, seabed topography	D1 / 1.6.3 D7 / 7.2.2
Mixed layer depth	Water column mixing characteristics	D1 / 1.6.3
Maximum density gradient	Water column mixing characteristics	D1 / 1.6.3
Physically sensitive Area index (PSA)	Vulnerability to eutrophication	D5 monitoring
OXYRISK	Oxygen depletion risk index at depth	D5 / 5.3.2 monitoring
Water temperature (SST and bottom temperature)	Hydrographical conditions	D1 / 1.6.3
Bottom salinity	Hydrographical conditions	D1 / 1.6.3
Seabed habitat	Extent and proportion of benthic habitats	D1 / 1.4.1; 1.4.2; 1.5.1; 1.5.2; 1.7.1 D6 / 6.1.1; 6.1.2
Spawning habitat (bluefin tuna)	Extent of potential spawning habitat	D1 / 1.5.1 D3 / 3.2.1 monitoring
Feeding habitat (bluefin & skipjack tuna, hake, fin whale)	Extent of potential feeding habitat	D1 / 1.5.1 D3 / 3.2.1 monitoring

647

648

649 **Table 3.** Description by fish species of favorable habitats products presently inserted within
650 EMIS.

651

Fish species	Habitat type	Area covered	Period covered
Atlantic Bluefin tuna (adults)	Feeding and spawning	North Atlantic, Mediterranean Sea	2003-2013
Atlantic Bluefin tuna (juveniles)	Feeding	North Atlantic, Mediterranean Sea	2003-2013
Skipjack tuna	Feeding	Central east Atlantic	1998-2013
Hake nurseries	Feeding	Mediterranean Sea	2003-2015
Fin whale	Feeding	West Mediterranean Sea	2003-2015

652

653

654 **List of Figures**

655

656 **Figure 1.** Web-GIS viewer layout structure. 1. Display window; 2. Control bar (selection of
657 variables with time and spatial attributes; navigation and data interrogating tools); 3. Left menu
658 panel (detailed elements of each of the 4 tool bar options); 4. Data dissemination tool panel.

659

660 **Figure 2.** Architecture and technical workflow of the Geoportal EMIS and its associated
661 tools.

662

663 **Figure 3.** Local map of the protected area “Bouches de Bonifacio, Iles des Moines”. The
664 area is 100% marine located at the southern tip of Corsica and includes waters surrounding
665 the small islands “Ilots des Moines”.

666

667 **Figure 4.** 3D-viewing of the local bathymetry within and around the marine protected area
668 “Bouches de Bonifacio, Iles des Moines”.

669

670 **Figure 5.** Local map of seabed habitats obtained by aggregation of two sources of
671 information: EUNIS seafloor habitat classes and UNEP’s Global seafloor Geomorphic
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674 **Figure 6.** (a) Time-series of monthly sea surface temperature (SST, in °C) as derived from
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676 concentration (in mg.m⁻³) as derived from the sensor MODIS-Aqua for the period 2005-2015.

677

678 **Figure 7a.** Maps of monthly sea surface temperature anomalies with respect to monthly
679 climatology calculated over the full MODIS-Terra time series as available in EMIS (i.e.
680 complete years from 2001 to 2016).

681

682 **Figure 7b.** Maps of monthly chlorophyll-a anomalies with respect to monthly climatology
683 calculated over the full MODIS-Aqua time series as available in EMIS (i.e. complete years
684 from 2003 to 2016).

685

686 **Figure 8.** Monthly climatology of modeled bottom salinity (a) and bottom temperature (b)
687 within and around the BBIM marine protected area.

688

689 **Figure 9.** Density of alien species within and in the vicinity of the Bonifacio marine
690 protected area. Data are extracted from the European Alien Species Information Net work
691 (EASIN).